

Explicit Momentum and Energy Conservation in Quantum Bound States

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A nonrelativistic classical bound state is characterized by a conservation of energy equation: $p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E$. There is no explicit momentum conservation, but there is implicit because $F = dp/dt$ together with action-reaction implies momentum conservation.

We suggest that quantum bound states differ from classical because of explicit momentum conservation as well as explicit average conservation of energy. This momentum conservation is complicated because each momentum state is characterized by $\exp(ipx)$ which implies a wavelength in space of \hbar/p . Thus, in the quantum case, there is the usual: $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n$, but $KE_{ave}(x)$ is created by using $\exp(ipx)$ s which conserve momentum when hits occur with $V(x)$. This may be seen explicitly by writing the Schrodinger equation for each $\exp(ipx)$ weight. The bound state is one in which there is an average conservation of energy through momentum conserving hits with a potential $V(x)$. The fact that there is a wavelength associated with $\exp(ipx)$, a momentum conserving probability, seems to be linked to the idea that p need not be measured by clock so the classical action $A = -Et + px$ (both relativistic and nonrelativistic for a free particle) must have independent t and x . For this to occur $px = \text{constant}$ and $-Et = \text{constant}^2$, implying $x = n/p$ and $t = n/E$. In other words, one may have a constant only for repeated length or time intervals if one uses a periodic function. For p , this periodicity in space characterizes p_1 from p_2 and this is linked to momentum conservation or the orthogonality of $\exp(ip_1x)$ and $\exp(ip_2x)$. Otherwise, there would be no need to have p linked with a wavelength, which is something that does not occur in classical physics.

Classical Bound State and Implicit Momentum Conservation

A classical bound state is solved by using a conservation of energy equation:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

There is no explicit notion of conservation of momentum in ((1)). A particle moving to the right with $p(x)$ at x changes to $p(x+dx)$ at $x+dx$ meaning that its momentum has changed but one does not explicitly see the momentum appear anywhere. On the other hand, the change of $V(x)$ explicitly represents the kinetic energy lost by the particle. We suggest that a more complete picture should perhaps include both conservation of momentum and energy.

The Idea of the Wavelength and Conservation of Momentum

The idea of conservation of momentum and energy already exists in classical physics and does not seem to have anything to do with a wavelength or time period. In fact, these seem to be usual. We have noted before, however, that another unusual feature, this time in classical mechanics, is that p a dynamic variable which cannot exist if there is no velocity, but p does not require a clock for its measurement, whereas v does. In fact, the same p may correspond to different rest mass, v pairs and is measured by an impulse hit (i.e the striking of target and

assessing the damage). If this is the case, then even though a given rest mass m_0 with a velocity v has an energy and momentum, one should be able to split the classical action into t independent pieces. The relativistic or nonrelativistic action for a free particle is (using $v=x/t$):

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

For px and $-Et$ to be independent mathematically, they should be constants, i.e.

$$t = n \hbar / E \quad \text{and} \quad x = n \hbar / p \quad ((3))$$

There is a resolution of \hbar/E and \hbar/p and a periodic function $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ characterizes p from p_1 through orthogonality. Thus, the wavelength is linked to momentum conservation.

The Quantum Bound State

The Schrodinger (time-independent) equation may be written as:

$$KEave(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

((4)) holds for all energy levels and is a conservation of energy type equation. Where is conservation of momentum?

We suggest that a single particle interacts with $V(x)$ through momentum hits which must conserve momentum. These must be displayed explicitly. If $\exp(ipx)$ represents a momentum conserving probability, then $\exp(ikx)$ represents a k momentum probability form $V(x)$. Thus, writing:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((5))$$

is not simply a Fourier series breakdown, but writes $V(x)$ in terms of momentum conserving probabilities. The weight V_k is energy because one is weighting each V_k by its corresponding momentum corresponding probability. With momentum conservation, one has a specific momentum p which is linked to energy, but also to interactions with $V(x)$ which conserve momentum. Given that $V(x)$ gives momentum hits, it is actually $\exp(i(p-k)x)$ momenta which become $\exp(kpx)$. Thus:

$$a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) + \exp(ipx) \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k a(p-k) = a(p) E_n \exp(kpx) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) may be summed over different $\exp(ipx)$ values to create the Schrodinger equation. Thus, there is more information in the Schrodinger equation than in a classical conservation of energy equation, we argue.

High En Limit

In the high En limit, the quantum spatial resolution of $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and the resolution of the dominant $\exp(ipx)$ values becomes very small. In such a case, one may consider an $\exp(ipx)$ to be localized at a given x with an impulse occurring there which conserves momentum. One no longer needs to show conservation of momentum explicitly and hence uses only the conservation of energy equation:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((7))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that classical mechanics only uses an explicit conservation of energy equation, with momentum conservation being implicit. We suggest that it might be good to have explicit energy and momentum conservation which is what quantum mechanics offers. The main feature, however, is that momentum conservation does occur at a point. If the two momenta involved are very high, then spatial resolution is very high and it seems that everything occurs at points. Given that the classical dynamical variable p does not need a clock for measurement, but must contain v which does, we suggest that the free particle action must be separable and independent in t, x , i.e. $A = -Et + px$ (relativistic and nonrelativistic). This means $t = \hbar n/E$ and $x = \hbar n/p$, i.e. there are resolutions in time and space in order to have this independence. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ in space with $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ip_1x)$ being orthogonal to represent conservation of momentum.

In quantum bound problems, a particle interacts with $V(x)$ through momentum conserving interactions. One has $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ikx)$ from $V(x)$. $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ shows the energy weight linked with the momentum conserving probability. One may write a classical conservation of energy equation for all n energy levels, i.e. $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n$, but including momentum conservation with energy conservation yields:

$\exp(ipx) a(p) p^2/2m + \exp(ipx) \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = a(p) E_n \exp(ipx)$. This leads to the same time-independent Schrodinger equation, but shows explicit conservation of momentum and when summed over $\exp(ipx)$ s, explicit energy conservation. Thus, momentum conservation appears in the form of $KE_{ave}(x)$ used i.e. $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W$, where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

For high En, spatial resolution becomes high and one may consider a p in each dx which receives a hit which conserves energy with momentum conservation again becoming implicit and one obtains the classical approximation